

RETALT

RETro propulsion Assisted Landing Technologies

KEY TECHNOLOGIES FOR RETRO PROPULSIVE VERTICAL DESCENT AND LANDING - RETALT -

AN OVERVIEW

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The Name

RETALT

RETro propulsion Assisted Landing Technologie

Overview

- Funded by the EU in the frame of Horizon 2020
- Lead by DLR
- Carried out by 6 Partners:
DLR · Almatech · Amorim Cork Composites
CFS Engineering · Deimos Space · MT Aerospace
- Started 6th of March 2019 – Ends in August 2022

3.5

YEARS

6

PARTNERS

4

COUNTRIES

3

MILLIONS (BUDGET)

Main Objectives

- To investigate the launch system reusability of
- Operational launch vehicle
Vertical Take-off Vertical Landing (VTVL) Two Stage To Orbit (TSTO)
(inspired by Falcon 9)
 - **RETALT1**
- Future launch vehicle (technology test bed)
Vertical Take-off Vertical Landing (VTVL) Single Stage To Orbit (SSTO)
(inspired by DC-X)
 - **RETALT2**

Key Technologies

- Aerodynamics and Aerothermodynamics
 - Aerodynamic Database (AEDB)
 - Aerothermodynamic Database (ATDB)
- GNC concept
- Structures and Mechanisms
 - Tested demonstrator of deployment mechanisms and structure
 - of aerodynamic control surfaces (Scale approx. 1/5)
 - of landing legs (Scale approx. 1/5)
- TPS for base plane and critical structural parts
 - TPS with new mounting technique (trowelable) tested in arc-heated facility (L2K)

Partners

- Coordination and Management
- Reference Configurations
- Aerodynamics and Aerothermodynamics:
 - CFD in Göttingen
 - Wind Tunnel Tests in Cologne
 - AEDB, ATDB

- CFD for aerodynamic loads
- Control surface efficiency
- Extrapolation to flight
- AEDB, ATDB
- Dissemination

- Mission analysis
- Flying Qualities Analyses
- GNC Concept and Control laws
- Definition of landing loads

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Partners

- Structural concept and design
- Design and Manufacturing of landing leg and control surface demonstrators
- Hardware for aerothermodynamic wind tunnel tests

- Thrust Vector Control (TVC)
- Mechanisms:
 - Landing legs
 - Aerodynamic control surfaces

- Thermal Protection System:
 - Cork based thermal protection of critical structural components
 - Development of trowelable technique

RETALT1

- Two Stage To Orbit (TSTO) Vertical Take-off Vertical Landing (VTVL) RLV
- Payload capacity: 14t to Geostationary Transfer Orbit (GTO)
 - LOX/LH2 Gas Generator (GG) engines (similar to the Vulcain 2)
 - Stage 1: 9 engines
 - Stage 2: 1 engine (similar to first stage engine)
 - Stage 1 engines adapted to sea level conditions - 1179 kN Thrust (SL)
 - Stage 2 engine adapted to vacuum conditions - 1364 kN thrust (Vac)
 - Height: 103 m
 - Diameter: 6 m
 - Take-off Mass: 899 t
 - Retro propulsion and the novel aerodynamic control surfaces (interstage segment)

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RETALT1

Stage Characteristics	1st Stage	2nd Stage	Fairing	Total
Number of Engines	9	1.0	-	10.0
Reusability	+	+/-	-	+/-
Height [m]	71.2	19.8	12.0	103.0
Diameter [m]	6.00	6.00		6.00
Mass full (GLOW) [t] (incl. Payload)	680.8	204.2	2.5	899.0
Stage Rate	75.7%	24.3%		
Structure Coefficient	8.7%	8.3%		
Mass structure [t]	59.3	16.7		75.9
Propellant mass (incl. descent propellant) [t]	621.5	187.5		809.0
Descent propellant [t]	50.0	0		50.0
Propellant reserve and residuals mass [t]	7.500	2.500		10.0
Engines	RETALT1-LHLOX-E15-FS	RETALT1-LHLOX-E70-FS		
Engine Cycle	Gasgenerator	Gasgenerator		
Oxidator/Propellant	LOX/LH2	LOX/LH2		
Expansion Ratio	15	70		
Specific Impuls SL [s]	372.2	294.4		
Specific Impuls Vac [s]	401.6	431.9		
Thrust SL [kN]	9x1179 = 10614	1x930 = 930		
Thrust Vac [kN]	9x1273 = 11453	1x1364 = 1364		

RETALT1

	Start of first breaking maneuver Altitude [km]	End of first breaking maneuver Mach [-]	propellant consumed [t]
Trajectory 70_4.6_1.9	70	4.6	~35.7
Trajectory 70_3.3_1.3	70	3.3	~44.8

Marwege, A.; Gülhan, A.; Klevanski, J.; Riehmer, J.; Kirchheck, D.; Karl, S.; Bonetti, D.; Vos, J.; Jevons, M.; Krammer, A.; Carvalho, J.: „Retro Propulsion Assisted Landing Technologies (RETALT): Current Status and Outlook of the EU Funded Project on Reusable Launch Vehicles“, 70th International Astronautical Congress (IAC), Washington D.C., United States, 21-25 October 2019.

RETALT2

- Single Stage to Orbit (SSTO) Vertical Take-off Vertical Landing (VTVL) RLV
- Payload capacity: 0.5t to Low Earth Orbit (LEO)
 - LOX/LH2 engine (similar to Vinci) adapted to sea level conditions
 - 9 identical engines - 370 kN thrust (Vac)
 - More academically: „technology test bed“
 - Retro propulsion + novel aerodynamic control surfaces (fairing section)
 - Aerodynamic braking: capsule-like shape + fairing segments
 - Nozzle exits flush with base plane of the vehicle
 - Height: 17.6 m
 - Diameter: 7.4 m
 - Take-off Mass: 79.4 t

Comparison of RETALT1 and RETALT2

RETALT2

500 kg to LEO

Blue Origin New Glenn:
Geostationary Transfer Orbit

13 MT

RETALT1

14 t to GTO

**Grasshopper from: Flickr of Steve Jurvetson, accessed 16.05.2022
<https://www.flickr.com/photos/jurvetson/7971310054/>

*Comparison taken from Blue Origin

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RETALT1 return mission concept

* Graphic by DEIMOS

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RETALT2 return mission concept

Scenario R2 DRL

* Graphic by DEIMOS

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Trajectories

RETALT1

RETALT2

Exploitation timeline

Conclusion

- Strong multidisciplinary European project team
- Investigation in key technologies for vertical landing with retro propulsion
 - aerodynamics · aerothermodynamics · flight dynamics and GNC · structures · mechanisms · TVC · TPS
- Successful load tests of a landing leg demonstrator
 - Demonstrator exhibited at booth
- Wind Tunnel tests for the complete flight envelope (subsonic, transonic, hypersonic)
 - Models exhibited at booth
- Extensive CFD studies and rebuilding of Wind Tunnel tests and extrapolation to flight
- Studies of several aerodynamic control surfaces and demonstrator built
 - Demonstrator exhibited at booth
- Mission analysis and GNC concept in several loops
- Development of new cork based trowelable TPS material and performance validated in tests in arc-heated facility
 - Samples exhibited at booth
- Dissemination at FAR and in CEAS Journal
- Large potential for exploitation of results and rapid implementation of technologies

almatech

RETAL
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THANK YOU!

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